

Top 10 Natural Language Processing Trends in 2020

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FURTHER INVESTIGATIONS ON DEVELOPING AN ARABIC SENTIMENT LEXICON

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ABSTRACT

The availability of lexical resources is huge to accelerate and simplify the sentiment analysis in English. In Arabic, there are few resources and these resources are not comprehensive. Most of the current research efforts for constructing Arabic Sentiment Lexicon (ASL) depend on a large number of lexical entities. However, the coverage of all Arabic sentiment expressions can be applied using refined regular expressions rather than a large number of lexical entities. This paper presents an ASL that more comprehensive than the existing lexicons, for covering many expressions with different dialects including Franco-Arabic, and in the same time more compact. Also, this paper shows how to integrate different lexicons and to refine them. To enrich lexical entries with very robust morphological syntactical information, regular expressions, the weight of sentiment polarity and n-gram terms have been augmented to each.

KEYWORDS

Arabic Natural Language Processing, Arabic Sentiment Lexicon, Sentiment Analysis, Text Mining.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Pang and L. Lee, "Opinion mining and sentiment analysis," *Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval*, vol. 2, no. 1-2, pp. 1-135, 2008.
- [2] F. Mahyoub, M. Siddiqui and M. Y. Dahab, "Building an Arabic sentiment lexicon using semisupervised learning," *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 417--424, 2014.
- [3] G. Badaro, R. Baly, H. Hajj, N. Habash and W. El-Hajj, "A large scale Arabic sentiment lexicon for Arabic opinion mining," in *Proceedings of the EMNLP Workshop on Arabic Natural Language Processing (ANLP)*, Doha, 2014.
- [4] R. Eskander and O. Rambow, "SLSA: A sentiment lexicon for Standard Arabic," in *Proceedings of the 2015 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, Lisbon, 2015.
- [5] V. Hatzivassiloglou and K. McKeown, "Predicting the semantic orientation of adjectives," in *Proceedings of the 8th conference on European chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, p. 174–181, 1997.
- [6] P. D. Turney and M. L. Littman, "Unsupervised learning of semantic orientation from a hundredbillion-word corpus," *Technical Report EGB-1094*, National Research Council Canada, 2002.
- [7] C. Fellbaum, *Wordnet, an Electronic Lexical Database*, Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1998.
- [8] S.-M. Kim and E. Hovy, "Determining the Sentiment of Opinions," *Proceedings of COLING-04*, 20th International Conference on Computational Linguistics, p. 1367–1373, 2004.
- [9] A. Esuli and F. Sebastiani, "Determining the semantic orientation of terms through gloss analysis.," In *Proceedings of CIKM-05*, 14th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management, p. 617–624, 2005.
- [10] A. Esuli and F. Sebastiani, "Determining term subjectivity and term orientation for opinion mining," In *Proceedings of EACL-06*, 11th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 2006.
- [11] J. Kamps, M. Marx, R. J. Mokken and M. d. Rijke, "using wordnet to measure semantic orientation of adjectives," *Proceedings of LREC-04*, 4th International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation, vol. 4, p. 1115–1118, 2004.
- [12] A. Aqel, S. Alwadei and M. Dahab, "Building an Arabic Words Generator," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 112, no. 14, pp. 36-41, 2015. [13] M. Elhawary and M. Elfeky, "Mining Arabic Business Reviews," *IEEE International Conference on Data Mining Workshops*, p. 1108–1113, 2010.
- [14] M. Maamouri, A. Bies, T. Buckwalter and W. Mekki, "The penn arabic treebank: Building a largescale annotated arabic corpus," in *NEMLAR Conference on Arabic Language Resources and Tools*, 2004.
- [15] M. Thelwall, K. Buckley, G. Paltoglou and D. Cai, "Sentiment Strength Detection in Short Informal Text," *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, vol. 61, no. 12, 2010.
- [16] M. Abdul-Mageed and M. Korayem, "Automatic identification of subjectivity in morphologically rich languages: the case of Arabic," *Proceedings of the 1st workshop on computational approaches to subjectivity and sentiment analysis (WASSA)*, pp. 2-6, 2010.

- [17] A. El-Halees, "Arabic opinion mining using combined classification approach," the international Arab conference on information technology, pp. 10-13, 2011.
- [18] M. Elarnaoty, S. AbdelRahman and A. Fahmy, "A Machine Learning Approach For Opinion Holder Extraction Arabic Language," in CoRR, 2012.
- [19] M. Abdul-Mageed and M. Diab, "Toward building a large-scale Arabic sentiment lexicon," Proceedings of the 6th International Global WordNet Conference, 2012.
- [20] T. Wilson, J. Wiebe and P. Hoffmann, "Recognizing contextual polarity in phrase-level sentiment analysis," in Proceedings of the conference on Human Language Technology and Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, 2005.
- [21] A. Esuli and F. Sebastiani, "SentiWordNet: A publicly available resource for opinion mining," Proceedings of the 5th Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'06), p. 417–422, 2006.
- [22] M. Abdul-Mageed, M. Korayem and A. YoussefAgha, ""Yes we can?": Subjectivity Annotation and Tagging for the Health Domain," in Proceedings of the International Conference Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing RANLP, Hissar, Bulgaria, 2011.
- [23] HARF, "ARABIC LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGY CENTER (ALTEC)," 5 4 2012. [Online]. Available: http://www.alteccenter.org/page.php?pg=filesrepository/getRepository.php&main_cat=1&sub_cat=24. [Accessed 1 3 2016].
- [24] A. Aqel, S. Alwadei and M. Dahab, "Building an Arabic Words Generator," International Journal of Computer Applications, vol. 112, no. 14, pp. 36-41, 2015.
- [25] M. A. Siddiqui, M. Y. Dahab and O. A. Batarfi, "Building A Sentiment Analysis Corpus With Multifaceted Hierarchical Annotation," International Journal of Computational Linguistics (IJCL), vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 11-25, 2015.
- [26] C. Fellbaum, M. Alkhalifa, W. J. Black, S. Elkateb, A. Pease, H. Rodriguez and P. Vossen, "Introducing the Arabic WordNet Project," Proceedings of the 3rd Global Wordnet Conference, 2006.
- [27] N. Godbole, M. Srinivasaiah and S. Skiena, "Large-scale sentiment analysis for news and blogs," Proceedings of the International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media ICWSM, 2007.
- [28] A. Valitutti, C. Strapparava and O. Stock, "Developing Affective Lexical Resources," PsychNology, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 61-83 , 2004.
- [29] M. Rushdi-Saleh, M. T. Martín-Valdivia, L. A. U. López and J. M. Perea-Ortega, "OCA: Opinion Corpus for Arabic," Journal of The American Society for Information Science and Technology, vol. 62, no. 10, pp. 2045-2054, 2011.
- [30] Y. Yang, "Noise Reduction in a Statistical Approach to Text Categorization," Proceedings of SIGIR95, 18th ACM International Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval, pp. 256--263, 1995.
- [31] G. Salton, A. Wong and C. S. Yang, "A vector space model for automatic indexing," Commun. ACM , vol. 18, no. 11, pp. 613 - 620, 1975.
- [32] M. M. Boudabous, N. C. Kammoun, N. Khedher, L. H. Belguith and F. Sadat, "Arabic WordNet semantic relations enrichment through morpho-lexical patterns," in Communications, Signal Processing, and their Applications (ICCSPA), 2013 1st International Conference, Sharjah, 2013.

[33] C. Fellbaum, M. Alkhalifa, W. J. Black, S. Elkateb, A. Pease, H. Rodriguez and P. Vossen, "Introducing the Arabic WordNet Project," Proceedings of the 3rd Global Wordnet Conference, 2006.

[34] "WordNet 3.0 database statistics," [Online]. Available: <https://wordnet.princeton.edu/wordnet/man/wnstats.7WN.html#toc>. [Accessed 15 4 2013].

BENGALI INFORMATION RETRIEVAL SYSTEM (BIRS)

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ABSTRACT

Information Retrieval System is an effective process that helps a user to trace relevant information by Natural Language Processing (NLP). In this research paper, we have presented present an algorithmic Information Retrieval System(BIRS) based on information and the system is significant mathematically and statistically. This paper is demonstrated by two algorithms for finding out the lemmatization of Bengali words such as Trie and Dictionary Based Search by Removing Affix (DBSRA) as well as compared with Edit Distance for the exact lemmatization. We have presented the Bengali Anaphora resolution system using the Hobbs' algorithm to get the correct expression of information. As the actions of questions answering algorithms, the TF-IDF and Cosine Similarity are developed to find out the accurate answer from the documents. In this study, we have introduced a Bengali Language Toolkit (BLTK) and Bengali Language Expression (BRE) that make the easiest implication of our task. We have also developed Bengali root word's corpus, synonym word's corpus, stop word's corpus and gathered 672 articles from the popular Bengali newspapers 'The Daily Prothom Alo' which is our inserted information. For testing this system, we have created 19335 questions from the introduced information and got 97.22% accurate answer.

KEYWORDS

Bangla language Processing, Information retrieval, Corpus, Mathematics, and Statistics.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Singhal, A. (2001). "Modern information retrieval: A brief overview.", *IEEE Data Engineering Bulletin* 24(4), 35–43.
- [2] Croft, W.B., Metzler, D. & Strohman, T. (2009). "Search engines-information retrieval in practice.", Pearson education. <http://www.search-engines-book.com/>.
- [3] Salton, G., Wong, A., & Yang, C. S. (1975). "A vector space model for automatic indexing." *Communications of the ACM* 18(11), 613–620. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/361219.361220>.
- [4] Robertson & S.E. (1997) "Readings in information retrieval", The probability ranking principle in IR (pp. 281–286). San Francisco, CA, USA: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc. <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=275537.275701>.
- [5] Robertson, S. E., & Jones, K. S. (1988) "Relevance weighting of search terms" (pp. 143–160). London, UK: Taylor Graham Publishing.
- [6] Amati, G., & Van Rijsbergen, C. J. (2002). "Probabilistic models of information retrieval based on measuring the divergence from randomness." *ACM Transactions on Information Systems* 20(4), 357–389.
- [7] Robertson, S. (2010). "The probabilistic relevance framework: BM25 and Beyond." *Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval* 3(4), 333–389.
- [8] Lavrenko, V., & Croft, W. B. (2001) "Relevance-based language models." In W. B. Croft, D. J. Harper, D.H.Kraft, & J.Zobel (eds.) *SIGIR2001: Proceedings of the 24th annual international ACM SIGIR conference on research and development in information retrieval*, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA (pp.120–127). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/383952.383972>.
- [9]. Agichtein, E., Brill, E., & Dumais, S. (2006) "Improving web search ranking by incorporating user behavior information." , *Proceedings of the 29th annual international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval, SIGIR 2006* (pp. 19–26). New York, NY, USA: ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1148170.1148177>.
- [10] Sivic, J., & Zisserman, A. (2003) "Videogoogle: A text retrieval approach to object matching in videos." , *Proceedings of the ninth IEEE international conference on computer vision, ICCV 2003* (Vol. 2, pp. 1470–1477). Washington, DC, USA: IEEE Computer Society. <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=946247.946751>.
- [11] Xu, S., Bao, S., Fei, B., Su, Z., & Yu, Y. (2008). "Exploring folksonomy for personalized search." , *Proceedings of the 31st annual international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval, SIGIR 2008* (pp. 155–162). New York, NY, USA: ACM
- [12] M. K. I.Molla, & K. M.Talukder, (2007) "Bangla number extraction and recognition from the document image" , *International Conference. on Computer and Information Technology, ICCIT 2007*, pp. 512-517.
- [13] M. S. Islam, (2009) "Research on Bangla Language Processing in Bangladesh: Progress and

Challenges”, International Conference on Language & Development pp. 23-25.

[14] M.A. Hasnat, S.M. Habib, & M. Khan (2008) “A high-performance domain specific OCR for Bangla script”, Novel Algorithms and Techniques In Telecommunications, Automation and Industrial Electronics pp. 174-178, Springer, Dordrecht International Journal on Natural Language Computing (IJNLC) Vol.8, No.5, October 2019 12

[15] G. Fink, S. Vajda, U. Bhattacharya, S. K. Parui & B. B. Chaudhuri, (2010). “ Online Bangla word recognition using sub-stroke level features and hidden Markov models” International Conference. on Frontiers in Handwriting Recognition, ICFHR 2010, pp. 393-398.

[16] K .Sarkar, (2012) “Bengali text summarization by sentence extraction”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1201.224.

[17] A. Das & S. Bandyopadhyay, (2010). “Phrase-level Polarity Identification for Bengali” International Journal of Computational Linguistics and Applications, IJCLA, 1(1-2), pp. 169-182.

[18] U. Bhattacharya, S. K. Parui, & S. Mondal, (2009) “Devanagari and Bangla Text Extraction from Natural Scene Images”, International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition, pp. 171- 175.

[19] A. Hassan, M.R. Amin, N. Mohammed, & A.K.A. Azad, (2016). “Sentiment Analysis on Bangla and Romanized Bangla Text (BRBT) using Deep Recurrent models”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1610.00369

PRONOUN DISAMBIGUATION: WITH APPLICATION TO THE WINOGRAD SCHEMA CHALLENGE

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ABSTRACT

A value-based approach to Natural Language Understanding, in particular, the disambiguation of pronouns, is illustrated with a solution to a typical example from the Winograd Schema Challenge. The worked example uses a language engine, Enguage, to support the articulation of the advocacy and fearing of violence. The example illustrates the indexical nature of pronouns, and how their values, their referent objects, change because they are set by contextual data. It must be noted that Enguage is not a suitable candidate for addressing the Winograd Schema Challenge as it is an interactive tool, whereas the Challenge requires a preconfigured, unattended program.

KEYWORDS

Natural Language Understanding, Winograd Schema Challenge, Enguage, Interactive Computation, Peircean Semiotics

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REFERENCES

- [1] Levesque, H., Davis, E., Morganstern, L. (2019), see <http://commonsensereasoning.org/winograd.html> (Retrieved 25th Sept 2019)
- [2] Wikipedia (2019), https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Winograd_Schema_Challenge, (Retrieved 25th Sept 2019)
- [3] IBM (2019) <https://www.ibm.com/watson/how-to-build-a-chatbot> retrieved 3rd Oct 2019
- [4] Apple (2019) <https://www.apple.com/uk/siri/> retrieved 3rd Oct 2019
- [5] Amazon (2019) <https://developer.amazon.com/en-US/alexa/alexa-skills-kit> retr., 3rd Oct 2019
- [6] Cucumber (2019) <https://cucumber.io/docs>, retrieved 3rd Oct, 2019
- [7] Wheatman, M. J. (2019) Building Conversational Interfaces, ITNOW, Volume 61, Issue 1, Spring 2019, Pages 48–49, <https://doi.org/10.1093/itnow/bwz020>
- [8] Wheatman, M. J. (2014). An Autopoietic Repertoire. In: Bramer, M., Petridis, M. (Eds.), *Research and Development in Intelligent Systems XXXI: Proceedings of the 34th SGAI International Conference on Innovative Techniques and Applications of Artificial Intelligence* (pp 165-170). Cambridge, UK: Springer. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-12069-0
- [9] Wheatman, M. J. (2018) Unifying Speech and Computation, In Liu K., Nakata K., Li W., Baranauskas C. (eds) *Digitalisation, Innovation, and Transformation, ICISO 2018. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology, Vol 527*, Springer, pp 167-176
- [10] Wheatman, M. J.(2019), <https://github.com/martinwheatman/Enguage.jar>, retrieved Oct., 3rd
- [11] Loebner, H. G. (1994) In Response, *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 37 Issue 6, 37(6) 1994
- [12] Peirce, C. S. (1955) *Logic as Semiotic: The Theory of Signs*, *Philosophical Writings of Peirce*, Ed., J. Buchler, Dover Publications, New York, Pp 98-100
- [13] Wheatman, M. J. (2018) On Because and Why: Reasoning with Natural Language *International Journal of Conceptual Structures and Smart Applications*, Vol. 6, Issue 2, July-Dec 2018, DOI: 10.4018/IJCSSA.2018070101
- [14] Codd, E. F. (1970). A Relational Model of Data for Large Shared Data Banks. *Communications of the ACM*, 13(6), 377–387, DOI:10.1145/362384.362685d.
- [15] Saussure, F. de (1983) *A Course in General Linguistics* (C. Bally & A. Sechehaye, Eds., R. Harris, Trans.). London: Duckworth. (Original work published 1916).
- [16] Palme, J. (1970) *SIMULA 67: An advanced programming and simulation language*, Norwegian Computing Centre Publication.
- [17] Andersen, P. B. (1990) *A Theory of Computer Semiotics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

[18] Austin, J. L. (1962) *How to Do Things with Words*. (Eds.). Oxford: Oxford University Press.

[19] Smith, N. (2019) https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/fss/courses/ling/corpus/blue/clc_top.htm Retrieved 3rd October, 2019.

[20] Morris, C. W. (1938) *Foundations of the Theory of Signs*, *Encyclopaedia of Unified Science*, 1(2), University of Chicago, Chicago.

AUTO CORRECTION OF SETSWANA REAL-WORD ERRORS

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ABSTRACT

Spell checkers are used to detect and where possible correct spelling errors. Errors are classified as nonword errors and real-word errors. Real-word errors require the consideration of the context of the sentence to detect and correct. Setswana language has several commonly used words which are often misspelled by either separating or merging them. The misspelling results in real-word errors. In this paper we propose contextual rules that look at neighbor words to determine whether the correct word is written as two separate words or merged as one word. For some words the rules require that the parts of speech category of neighbor words be determined whereas some depend on specific neighbor words or position in a sentence. Implemented rules show that the rules are very consistent with a 88% success rate. Our tool only looks at neighbor words and therefore does not look at the context of the whole sentence. Hence, for words that require context of the whole sentence to disambiguate correctly our rules fail. This module can be incorporated into a spell checker to detect and correct real world errors for some words. That is, help users to determine the correct orthography of certain words.

KEYWORDS

Spell checker, real-word errors, dictionary.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Dr. G. Malema is a Senior lecturer at the Department of Computer Science, University of Botswana. He obtained his PhD Computer Engineering in 2008 from K. Kukich, “Techniques for automatically correcting words in text”, *ACM Computing Surveys*, (24(4), pp 277-439, 1992.
- [2] P.H Hema & C. Sunitha, “Spell Checker for non-word Error Detection: Survey”, *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, Vol 5, Issue 3, March 2015.
- [3] Graeme Hirst and Alexander Budanitsky, “Correcting real-word spelling errors by restoring lexical cohesion”, *Natural Language Engineering*, 11(1): 87—111 2005
- [4] Mashod Rana, Mohammad Sultan and M.F Mridha,” Detection and Correction of Real-word Errors in Bangla Language”, *International Conference on Bangla Speech and Language Processing* September 2018.
- [5] D J Prinsloo and Gilles-Maurice deSchryver, “Non-word error detection in current South African Spellcheckers”. *South African Linguistics and Applied Language Studies*, 21(4):307—326 2003
- [6] Leon Grobbelaar,”A study on creating a custome South Sotho Spelling and Correcting Software Desktop Application”, *Master of Technology Dissertation 2007*, Central University of Technology, Free State, South Africa.
- [7] Mogapi, K, “Thuto Puo ya Setswana”, Longman Botswana, 184, ISBN:0582 619033
- [8] Malema G, Motlogelwa N, Okgetheng B, Mogotlhwane O, “Setswana Verb Analyzer and Generator”, *International Journal of Computational Linguistics (IJCL)*, Vol 7, issue 1, 2016

HANDLING CHALLENGES IN RULE BASED MACHINE TRANSLATION FROM MARATHI TO ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Machine translation is being carried out by the researchers from quite a long time. However, it is still a dream to materialize flawless Machine Translator and the small numbers of researchers has focussed at translating Marathi Text to English. Perfect Machine Translation Systems have not yet been fully built owing to the fact that languages differ syntactically as well as morphologically. Majority of the researchers have opted for Statistical Machine translation whereas in this paper we have addressed the challenges of Rule based Machine Translation. The paper describes the major divergences observed in language Marathi and English and many challenges encountered while attempting to build machine translation system form Marathi to English using rule based approach and rules to handle these challenges. As there are exceptions to the rules and limit to the feasibility of maintaining knowledgebase, the practical machine translation from Marathi to English is a complex task.

KEYWORDS

NLP; Machine Translation; English; Marathi; grammar.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Sinha, R. M. K., & Thakur, A., 2005c, Divergence patterns in machine translation between Hindi and English, Proceeding of MT Summit X. Phuket, Thailand, pp. 346-353
- [2] S. B. Kulkarni, P. D. Deshmukh, M. M. Kazi, K. V. Kale, "Linguistic to Socio-And-Psyco Linguistic Aspects in English-To-Marathi Language Translation", International Journal of Research in Computer Applications And Robotics, 2013; 1(9), pp.197-205
- [3] S. B. Kulkarni, P. D. Deshmukh and K. V. Kale, "Syntactic and Structural Divergence in English-to-Marathi Machine Translation", IEEE 2013 International Symposium on Computational and Business Intelligence, August 24-26, 2013, New Delhi, pp. 191-194,doi: 10.1109/ISCBI.2013.46
- [4] G.V. Garje, G.K. Kharate,"Challenges in Rule Based Machine Translation from English to Marathi", 3rd International Conference on Recent Trends in Engineering &Technology (ICRTET'2014),pp. 243-248.
- [5] Namrata G Kharate, Dr.Varsha H. Patil "Survey of Machine Translation for Indian Languages to English and Its Approaches" International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology ,Volume 3,Issue 1,ISSN : 2456-3307,pp. 613-622.
- [6] Joshi A., Sasikumar N. Constructive approach to teach inflections in Marathi language, Proceedings of National Conference on Advances in Technology andRecent Developments, Mumbai, India, 2008, pp.10-16
- [7] Khan Md., Anwarus S., Amada S., Nishino T. Sublexical Translations for low-resource language, Proceedings of Workshop on Machine Translation andParsing in Indian Languages (MTPIL-2012), 24th International Conference on Computer Linguistics (Coling12)
- [8] M. R. Walimbe. Sugam Marathi VyakranLekhan, G.Y. Rane Publication
- [9] Wren P., Martin H. High School English Grammar and Composition, S Chand Publication
- [10] CharugatraTidke, Shital B, Shivani P (2013) "Inflection Rules for English to Marathi Machine Translation"IJCSMC, Vol. 2, Issue. 4, April 2013, pg.7 – 18
- [11] EshaPalta IITB. Word Sense Disambiguation, 2006-07, Master of Technology First Stage Report.
- [12] Walker D. and Amsler R. 1986. The Use of Machine Readable Dictionaries in Sublanguage Analysis. In Analyzing Language in Restricted Domains, Grishmanand Kittredge (eds), LEA Press, pp. 69-83
- [13] Namrata G Kharate,Dr.Varsha H. Patil " Challenges in Rule Based Machine Translation from Marathi to English " 5th International Conference on Advances in Computer Science and Information Technology (ACSTY-2019), August 17-18, 2019.pp 45-54

SENTIMENT ANALYSIS ON PRODUCT FEATURES BASED ON LEXICON APPROACH USING NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

Sentiment analysis has played an important role in identifying what other people think and what their behavior is. Text can be used to analyze the sentiment and classified as positive, negative or neutral. Applying the sentiment analysis on the product reviews on e-market helps not only the customer but also the industry people for taking decision. The method which provides sentiment analysis about the individual product's features is discussed here. This paper presents the use of Natural Language Processing and SentiWordNet in this interesting application in Python: 1. Sentiment Analysis on Product review [Domain: Electronic]2. sentiment analysis regarding the product's feature present in the product review [Sub Domain: Mobile Phones]. It uses a lexicon based approach in which text is tokenized for calculating the sentiment analysis of the product reviews on a e-market. The first part of paper includes sentiment analyzer which classifies the sentiment present in product reviews into positive, negative or neutral depending on the polarity. The second part of the paper is an extension to the first part in which the customer review's containing product's features will be segregated and then these separated reviews are classified into positive, negative and neutral using sentiment analysis. Here, mobile phones are used as the product with features as screen, processors, etc. This gives a business solution for users and industries for effective product decisions.

KEYWORDS

Sentiment Analysis, Natural Language Processing, SentiWordNet, lexicon based approach

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REFERENCES

- [1] Allen, James, "Natural Language Understanding", Second edition (Redwood City: Benjamin/Cummings, 1995).
- [2] Baxendale, P. (1958). Machine-made index for technical literature - an experiment. IBM Journal of Research Development, 2(4):354–361. [2, 3, 5]
- [3] Bird Steven, Klein Ewan, Loper Edward June 2009, "Natural Language Processing with Python", Pages 16,27,79
- [4] Cortez Eli, Altigran S da da Silva 2013, " Unsupervised Information Extraction by Text Segmentation", Ch 3
- [5] Kumar Ela, "Artificial Intelligence", Pages 313-315
- [6] Goddard Cliff Second edition 2011, "Semantic Analysis: A practical introduction ", Section 1.1- 1.5
- [7] Lukaszewski Albert 2010, "MySQL for Python", Ch 1,2,3
- [8] Manning Christopher D., SchützeHinrich Sixth Edition 2003, "Foundations of Statistical Natural Language Processing", Ch 4 Page no. 575
- [9] Martelli Alex Second edition July 2006, "Python in a Nutshell", Pages 44,201.
- [10] Natural Language Toolkit, Retrieved from <http://www.nltk.org> [11] Pattern 2.6, Retrieved from <http://www.clips.ua.ac.be/pattern>
- [12] Prasad Reshma, Mary Priya Sebastian, International Journal on Natural Language Computing (IJNLC) Vol. 3, No.2, April 2014, " A survey on phrase structure learning methods for text classification"
- [13] Python Language, Retrieved from <https://www.python.org/>
- [14] Rodrigues Mário , Teixeira António , "Advanced Applications of Natural Language Processing for Performing ", Ch 1,2,4
- [15] Sobin Nicholas 2011, "Syntactic Analysis: The Basics", Ch 1,2
- [16] Swaroop C H, "A Byte of Python: Basics and Syntax of Python", Ch 5,8,9,10

- [17] TextBlob: Simplified Text Processing, Retrieved from <http://textblob.readthedocs.org/en/dev>
- [18] ThanosCostantino , "Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries", Page 338-362
- [19] Tosi Sandro November 2009, "Matplotlib for Python Developers", Ch 2,3
- [20] Aashutosh Bhatt et al, / (IJCSIT) International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, Vol. 6 (6) , 2015, 5107-5110
- [21] Akshaya R. Garjeet al, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science, 8(9), Nov– Dec, 2017,554-557
- [22] Andrea Esuli and Fabrizio Sebastiani. 2006. SENTIWORDNET:A publicly available lexical resource for opinion mining. In Proceedings of the 5th Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'06), pages 417–422, Genova, IT.
- [23] Bo Pang and Lillian Lee. 2008. Opinion mining and sentiment analysis. Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval, 2(1/2):1–135.

ATTENTION-BASED SYLLABLE LEVEL NEURAL MACHINE TRANSLATION SYSTEM FOR MYANMAR TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE PAIR

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ABSTRACT

Neural machine translation is a new approach to machine translation that has shown the effective results for high-resource languages. Recently, the attention-based neural machine translation with the large scale parallel corpus plays an important role to achieve high performance for translation results. In this research, a parallel corpus for Myanmar-English language pair is prepared and attention-based neural machine translation models are introduced based on word to word level, character to word level, and syllable to word level. We do the experiments of the proposed model to translate the long sentences and to address morphological problems. To decrease the low resource problem, source side monolingual data are also used. So, this work investigates to improve Myanmar to English neural machine translation system. The experimental results show that syllable to word level neural machine translation model obtains an improvement over the baseline systems

KEYWORDS

Attention-based NMT, Syllable to word level NMT, Low resource language, Myanmar language.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kyunghyun Cho, Bart van Merriënboer, Caglar Gulcehre, Dzmitry Bahdanau, Fethi Bougares, holger Schwenk, Yoshua Bengio, (2014) "Learning phrase representations using RNN encoderdecoder for statistical machine translation", In Proceedings of EMNLP.
- [2] Dzmitry Bahdanau, KyungHyun Cho, Yoshua Bengio, (2015) "Neural machine translation by jointly learning to align and translate", In Proceedings of ACL – IJCNLP 2015, Volume 1: Long Papers.
- [3] Minh-Thang Luong, Christopher D. Manning, (2016) "Achieving Open Vocabulary Neural Machine Translation with Hybrid Word-Character Models", Proceedings of the 54th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, pages 1054–1063.
- [4] Thet Thet Zin, Khin Mar Soe, Ni Lar Thein, (2011) "Myanmar Phrases Translation Model with Morphological Analysis for Statistical Myanmar to English Translation System", 25th Pacific Asia Conference on Language, Information and Computation, pages 130–139.
- [5] Win Pa Pa, Ye Kyaw Thu, Andrew Finch, Eiichiro Sumita, (2016) "A Study of Statistical Machine Translation Methods for Under Resourced Languages", 29th Pacific Asia Conference on Language, Information and Computation pages 259 –269.
- [6] Jason Lee, Kyunghyun Cho, Thomas Hofmann, (2017) "Fully Character-Level Neural Machine Translation without Explicit Segmentation", Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics, vol. 5, pp. 365–378.
- [7] Jing Wu, Hongxu Hou, Zhipeng Shen, Jian Du, Jinting Li, (2011) "Adapting Attention-based Neural Network to Low-resource Mongolian-Chinese Machine Translation", Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.
- [8] Minh-Thang Luong, Hieu Pham, Christopher D. Manning, (2015) "Effective Approaches to Attention-based Neural Machine Translation", Proceedings of the 2015 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, pages 1412–1421.
- [9] Myanmar Language Committee, (2005) "Myanmar Grammar", Myanmar Language Committee, Ministry of Education, Myanmar.
- [10] Junyoung Chung, Kyunghyun Cho, Yoshua Bengio, (2016) "A character-level decoder without explicit segmentation for neural machine translation", In Proceedings of ACL.
- [11] Patrik Lambert, Holger Schwenk, Christopher Servan, Sadaf Abdul-Rauf, (2011) "Investigations on translation model adaptation using monolingual data", In Proceedings of the Sixth Workshop on Statistical Machine Translation, pages 284–293, Edinburgh, Scotland.
- [12] Guillaume Klein, Yoon Kim, Yuntian Deng, Jean Senellart, Alexander M. Rush, (2017) "OpenNMT: Open-Source Toolkit for Neural Machine Translation", Proceedings of the 55th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, pages 67–72, Vancouver, Canada, July 30-August 4, 2017.

- [13] Khin Thandar Nwet, Khin Mar Soe, (2016) "Myanmar-English Machine Translation Model", International Conference on Genetic and Evolutionary Computing (ICGEC): Genetic and Evolutionary Computing, pp 195-203.
- [14] Marta R. Costa-Jussà, Jose' A.R. Fonollosa, (2016) "Character-based Neural Machine Translation", Proceedings of the 54th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, pages 357–361.
- [15] Rico Sennrich, Barry Haddow, Alexandra Birch, A, (2016) "Improving neural machine translation models with monolingual data", In Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, pages 86–96.
- [16] Pytorch-OpenNMT, <http://github.com/OpenNMT/OpenNMT-py>.
- [17] Ye Kyaw Thu, (2017) Syllable segmentation tool for Myanmar language (Myanmar), <https://github.com/ye-kyaw-thu/sylbreak>.
- [18] UCSY_NLP lab segmenter, http://www.nlpresearch-ucsy.edu.mm/NLP_UCSY/wsandpos.html.
- [19] Yi Mon Shwe Sin, Khin Mar Soe, (2018) "Large Scale Myanmar to English Neural Machine Translation System", Proceeding of the IEEE 7th Global Conference on Consumer Electronic (GCCE 2018).
- [20] <http://lotus.kuee.kyoto-u.ac.jp/WAT/my-en-data>
- [21] <https://github.com/moses-smt/mosesdecoder/blob/master/scripts/tokenizer/tokenizer.perl>

BOOTSTRAPPING METHOD FOR DEVELOPING PART-OF-SPEECH TAGGED CORPUS IN LOW RESOURCE LANGUAGES TAGSET- A FOCUS ON AN AFRICAN IGBO

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ABSTRACT

Most languages, especially in Africa, have fewer or no established part-of-speech (POS) tagged corpus. However, POS tagged corpus is essential for natural language processing (NLP) to support advanced researches such as machine translation, speech recognition, etc. Even in cases where there is no POS tagged corpus, there are some languages for which parallel texts are available online. The task of POS tagging a new language corpus with a new tagset usually face a bootstrapping problem at the initial stages of the annotation process. The unavailability of automatic taggers to help the human annotator makes the annotation process to appear infeasible to quickly produce adequate amounts of POS tagged corpus for advanced NLP research and training the taggers. In this paper, we demonstrate the efficacy of a POS annotation method that employed the services of two automatic approaches to assist POS tagged corpus creation for a novel language in NLP. The two approaches are cross-lingual and monolingual POS tags projection. We used cross-lingual to automatically create an initial ‘errorful’ tagged corpus for a target language via word-alignment. The resources for creating this are derived from a source language rich in NLP resources. A monolingual method is applied to clean the induce noise via an alignment process and to transform the source language tags to the target language tags. We used English and Igbo as our case study. This is possible because there are parallel texts that exist between English and Igbo, and the source language English has available NLP resources. The results of the experiment show a steady improvement in accuracy and rate of tags transformation with score ranges of 6.13% to 83.79% and 8.67% to 98.37% respectively. The rate of tags transformation evaluates the rate at which source language tags are translated to target language tags.

KEYWORDS

Languages, Africa, Part-of-Speech, Corpus, Natural Language Processing, Tagset, Igbo, Bootstrapping.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Adams O., Makarucha A., Neubig G., Bird S., Cohn T., “Cross-lingual word embeddings for lowresource language modeling”, Proceedings of the 15th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Volume 1, Long Papers, vol. 1, p. 937-947, 2017.
- [2] Adedjouma S. A., John O. R. A., Mamoud I. A., “Part-of-Speech tagging of Yoruba Standard, Language of Niger-Congo family”, Research Journal of Computer and Information Technology Sciences, vol. 1, p. 2-5, 2013.
- [3] Agić Ž., Hovy D., Søgaard A., “If all you have is a bit of the Bible: Learning POS taggers for truly low-resource languages”, Proceedings of the 53rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and the 7th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (Volume 2: Short Papers), vol. 2, p. 268-272, 2015.
- [4] Agichtein E., Gravano L., “Snowball: Extracting relations from large plain-text collections”, Proceedings of the fifth ACM conference on Digital libraries, ACM, p. 85-94, 2000.
- [5] Atwell E., Hughes J., Souter D., “Amalgam: Automatic mapping among lexicogrammatical annotation models”, The Balancing Act: Combining Symbolic and Statistical Approaches to Language- Proceedings of the ACL Workshop, Association for Computational Linguistics, p. 21-20, 1994.
- [6] Bamba Dione C. M., Kuhn J., Zariëß S., “Design and Development of Part-of-Speech-Tagging Resources for Wolof (Niger-Congo, spoken in Senegal)”, Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC’10). Valletta, Malta, European Language Resources Association (ELRA), 2010.
- [7] Brill E., “Transformation-based error-driven learning and natural language processing: A case study in part-of-speech tagging”, Computational linguistics, vol. 21, no 4, p. 543-565, 1995.
- [8] Central Intelligence Agency, “The World FactBook”, <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/world-factbook/geos/ni.html>.
- [9] Chungku C., Rabgay J., Faaß G., “Building NLP resources for Dzongkha: a tagset and a tagged corpus”, Proceedings of the Eighth Workshop on Asian Language Resources, p. 103-110, 2010.
- [10] Department of Computer Science, Johns Hopkins Whiting School of Engineering, “An Introduction to Transformation-Based Learning”, <https://www.cs.jhu.edu/~rflorian/fntbl/tbl-toolkit/node3.html>.
- [11] Ethnologue, “Igbo”, <https://www.ethnologue.com/language/ibo>.
- [12] Girma A. D., Mesfin G., “Fast Development of Basic NLP Tools: Towards a Lexicon and a POS Tagger for Kurmanji Kurdish”, International Conference on Lexis and Grammar, Belgrade: Serbia (2010), p. 0, 2010.
- [13] IgboGuide.org. “Igbo Grammar”, <http://www.igboguide.org/HT-igbogrammar.htm>.
- [14] J. T., “The North-West University Bible corpus: A multilingual parallel corpus for South African languages.”, Language Matters, 2006.

- [15] Jeff A., “The Bible as a Resource for Translation Software: A proposal for MT development using an untapped language resource database”, *MultiLingual Computing and Technology*, 2002.
- [16] Moon T., Baldridge J., “Part-of-speech tagging for middle English through alignment and projection of parallel diachronic texts”, *Proceedings of the 2007 Joint Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing and Computational Natural Language Learning (EMNLP-CoNLL)*, 2007.
- [17] Ndiàmà Jehova, <https://www.jw.org/ig/>.
- [18] Ngai G., Florian R., “Transformation-based learning in the fast lane”, *Proceedings of the second meeting of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics on Language technologies*, Association for Computational Linguistics, p. 1-8, 2001.
- [19] Nichols C., Hwa R., “Word alignment and cross-lingual resource acquisition”, *Proceedings of the ACL Interactive Poster and Demonstration Sessions*, p. 69-72, 2005.
- [20] Och F. J., Ney H., “A Systematic Comparison of Various Statistical Alignment Models”, *Computational Linguistics*, vol. 29, no 1, p. 19-51, 2003.
- [21] Onyenwe I. E., *Developing Methods and Resources for Automated Processing of the African Language Igbo*, PhD thesis, University of Sheffield, 2017.
- [22] Onyenwe I. E., Hepple M., Chinedu U., Ezeani I., “A Basic Language Resource Kit Implementation for the Igbo NLP Project”, *ACM Transactions on Asian and Low-Resource Language Information Processing (TALLIP)*, vol. 17, no 2, p. 10, 2018.
- [23] Onyenwe I. E., Uchechukwu C., Hepple M., “Part-of-speech Tagset and Corpus Development for Igbo, an African”, *LAW VIIIp*. 93, 2014.
- [24] Onyenwe I., Hepple M., Uchechukwu C., Ezeani I., “Use of Transformation-Based Learning in Annotation Pipeline of Igbo, an African Language.”, *Joint Workshop on Language Technology for Closely Related Languages, Varieties and Dialects*, p. 24, 2015.
- [25] Resnik P., Olsen M., Diab M., “The Bible as a Parallel Corpus: Annotating the 'Book of 2000 Tongues'”, *Computers and the Humanities*. Springer, vol. 33, p. 29-153, 1999.
- [26] Tapas K., Philip R., “The Bible, Truth, and Multilingual OCR Evaluation”, in *Proc. of SPIE Conf. on Document Recognition and Retrieval*, p. 86-96, 1999.
- [27] Toutanova K., Klein D., Manning C. D., Singer Y., “Feature-rich part-of-speech tagging with a cyclic dependency network”, *Proceedings of the 2003 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics on Human Language Technology Volume 1*, Association for Computational Linguistics, p. 173-180, 2003.
- [28] Yarowsky D., Ngai G., Wicentowski R., “Inducing Multilingual Text Analysis Tools via Robust Projection Across Aligned Corpora”, *Proceedings of the First International Conference on Human Language Technology Research, HLT '01*, Association for Computational Linguistics, Stroudsburg, PA, USA, p. 1-8, 2001.

ISOLATING WORD LEVEL RULES IN TAMIL LANGUAGE FOR EFFICIENT DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

With the advent of social media, the amount of text available for processing across different natural languages has become enormous. In the past few decades, there has been tremendous increase in the number of language processing applications. The tools for natural language computing of various languages are very different because each language has its own set of grammatical rules. This paper focuses on identifying the basic inflectional principles of Tamil language at word level. Three levels of word inflection concepts are considered – Patterns, Rules and Exceptions. How grammatical principles for word inflections in Tamil can be grouped in these three levels and applied for obtaining different word forms is the focus of this paper. These can be made use of in a wide variety of natural language applications like morphological analysis, morphological generation, word level translation, spelling and grammar check, information extraction etc. The tools using these rules will account for faster operation and better implementation of Tamil grammatical rules referred from [த ால்த ாப்பியம் | tholgaappiyam] and [நன்னூல் | nannool] in NLP applications

KEYWORDS

Natural language processing, Rule based approach, word level rules, Tamil tool, language tools

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REFERENCES

- [1] Omnicore.[Online]. Available: <https://www.omnicoreagency.com/twitter-statistics/>
- [2] L.J.Brinton, The Structure Of Modern English: A Linguistic Introduction. Amsterdam, Philadelphia, PA: John Benjamins, 2000.
- [3] UC San Diego Linguistics Department.[Online]. Available: http://grammar.ucsd.edu/courses/lign120/08-intro_rev.pdf
- [4] S. Singh And V. M Sarma, “Hindi Noun Inflection And Distributed Morphology” In Proceedings Of The 17th International Conference On Head-Driven Phrase Structure Grammar, 2010, Pp. 307321
- [5] M. Ramscar , “The Role Of Meaning In Inflection: Why The Past-Tense Does Not Require A Rule,” Cognitive Psychology, Vol. 45, No. 1, Pp. 45–94, 2002.
- [6] Wikipedia.[Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agglutination>
- [7] Wikipedia.[Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agglutinative_language
- [8] S. C. Reddaiah. “Dravidian Languages And Its Fundamental Grammar,” Indian Journal Of Research, Vol. 3, No. 2, Pp. 164-166, 2014.
- [9] Anand Kumar M, Dhanalakshmi V, Soman K.P And Rajendran S, “A Sequence Labeling Approach To Morphological Analyzer For Tamil Language”, International Journal On Computer Science And Engineering, Vol. 2, No. 6, Pp. 1944 – 1951, 2010
- [10] P. Anandan, K. Saravanan, R.Parthasarathi And T. V. Geetha, “Morphological Analyzer For Tamil” In Proceedings Of International Conference On Natural Language Processing, 2002
- [11] Suriyah M, Aarthi Anandan, Anitha Narasimhan And Madhan Karky, “Piripori - Morphological Analyser For Tamil” In International Conference On Artificial Intelligence, Smart Grid And Smart City Applications, 2019.
- [12] [**எஞ்சியம்** | Kalanjiam].[Online]. Available: <http://store.tamillexicon.com>
- [13] Maanikkavaasakan, Tholkaappiyam, Chennai, TN : Uma Padhippagam, 2010
- [14] A. Manikkam, Nannool Kaandigaiyurai, Chennai, TN : Poompuhar Padhippagam, 1988
- [15] Seeni Naina Muhammad, Nalla Tamizh Ilakkanam, CITY, TN : Adayalam Padhippagam, 2013
- [16] Linguistic Data Consortium For Indian Languages. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ldcil.org/standardstextpos.aspx>

ANNOTATED GUIDELINES AND BUILDING REFERENCE CORPUS FOR MYANMAR- ENGLISH WORD ALIGNMENT

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ABSTRACT

Reference corpus for word alignment is an important resource for developing and evaluating word alignment methods. For Myanmar-English language pairs, there is no reference corpus to evaluate the word alignment tasks. Therefore, we created the guidelines for Myanmar-English word alignment annotation between two languages over contrastive learning and built the Myanmar-English reference corpus consisting of verified alignments from Myanmar ALT of the Asian Language Treebank (ALT). This reference corpus contains confident labels sure (S) and possible (P) for word alignments which are used to test for the purpose of evaluation of the word alignments tasks. We discuss the most linking ambiguities to define consistent and systematic instructions to align manual words. We evaluated the results of annotators agreement using our reference corpus in terms of alignment error rate (AER) in word alignment tasks and discuss the words relationships in terms of BLEU scores.

KEYWORDS

Annotation Guidelines, Alignment, Agreement, Reference Corpus, Treebank.

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REFERNCES

- [1] L. Macken, “An annotation scheme and Gold Standard for Dutch-English word alignment”, In 7th conference on International Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2010) (pp. 3369-3374). European Language Resources Association (ELRA). J. Clerk Maxwell, A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism, 3rd ed., vol. 2. Oxford: Clarendon, 1892, pp.68–73, 2010.
- [2] J. Li, D.I. Kim and J.H. Lee, “Annotation Guidelines for Chinese-Korean Word Alignment”, In LREC. May, 2008.
- [3] P. Lambert, A. De Gispert, R. Banchs and J.B. Mariño, “Guidelines for word alignment evaluation and manual alignment”, Language Resources and Evaluation, 39(4), pp.267-285, 2005.
- [4] I. Kruijff-Korbayová, K., Chvátalová and O., Postolache , “Annotation Guidelines for Czech-English Word Alignment”, In LREC , pp. 1256-1261, 2006.
- [5] Y.K., Thu, W.P. Pa, M. Utiyama, A.M., Finch and E. Sumita, “Introducing the Asian Language Treebank (ALT)”, In LREC, May, 2016.
- [6] P. Koehn, “Statistical machine translation”, Cambridge University Press, 2009.
- [7] P. Koehn, H. Hoang, A. Birch, C. Callison-Burch, M. Federico, N. Bertoldi, B. Cowan, W. Shen, C. Moran, R. Zens and C. Dyer, 2007, June. Moses: Open source toolkit for statistical machine translation. In Proceedings of the 45th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics companion volume proceedings of the demo and poster sessions (pp. 177-180).
- [8] A., Fraser and D. Marcu , “Measuring word alignment quality for statistical machine translation”, Computational Linguistics, 33(3), pp.293-303, 2007.
- [9] F.J. Och and H. Ney, “A systematic comparison of various statistical alignment models”, Computational linguistics, 29(1), pp.19-51. 2003.
- [10] P. F. Brown, S. A. Della Pietra, V. J. Della Pietra, and R. L. Mercer, “The mathematics of statistical machine translation: Parameter estimation”, Computational Linguistics, 19(2), pp.263–311. 1993.
- [11] M. L. Commission. “Myanmar Thdda, Department of the Myanmar Language Commission”, Ministry of Education, Union of Myanmar, 2005.
- [12] R.K. Yadav and D. Gupta, “Annotation guidelines for Hindi-English word alignment”, In 2010 International Conference on Asian Language Processing IEEE. pp. 293-296, December 2010. International Journal on Natural Language Computing (IJNLC) Vol.8, No.4, August 2019 38
- [13] R. Mihalcea and T. Pedersen, “An evaluation exercise for word alignment ”. In Proceedings of the HLT-NAACL 2003 Workshop on Building and using parallel texts: data driven machine translation and beyond, pp. 1-10, 2003.
- [14] I.D. Melamed, “Annotation style guide for the blinker project ”. arXiv preprint cmp-lg/9805004. 1998.
- [15] L. Ahrenberg, 2007. “Lines: An english-swedish parallel treebank ”. In Proceedings of the 16th

Nordic Conference of Computational Linguistics (NODALIDA 2007) pp. 270-273, 2007.

[16] <http://www2.nict.go.jp/astrecatt/member/mutiyama/ALT/index.html>

[17] L. Xuansong, G. Niyuge and S. Stephanie, “Guidelines for BOLT Chinese-English Word Alignment”, Version 2.0, pp. 1-35, 2014.

[18] Naing Tinnyuntpu, https://www.asiapearltravels.com/language/intro_burmese.php

[19] D. I. Melamed, 2001a, “Empirical methods for exploiting parallel texts”, MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

[20] D. I. Melamed. 2001b, “Manual annotation of translational equivalence”, In Dan I. Melamed, editor, Empirical methods for exploiting parallel texts, MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts. pp. 65-77.

[21] R. Mihalcea and T. Pedersen. “An Evaluation Exercise for Word Alignment”. In Proceedings of the HLT-NAACL 2003 Workshop on Building and Using Parallel Texts: Data Driven Machine Translation and Beyond, pages 1–10, Edmonton, Canada. pp. 1-10, 2003.

[22] J. V´eronis, “Evaluation of parallel text alignment systems: the ARCADE project”, In Jean V´eronis, editor, Parallel text processing: alignment and use of translation corpora, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht. pp. 369-388. 2000.

[23] L. Ahrenberg, M. Andersson, and M. Merkel, “ A system for incremental and interactive word linking”, In Proceedings of the third International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2002), pages 485–490, Las Palmas, Spain. pp. 485-490. 2002..